

Enabling Responsive Space: F-15 Microsatellite Launch Vehicle

Capt Nick Hague
Lt Erika Siegenthaler
Lt Julia Rothman
Air Force Research Laboratory, Space Vehicles
3550 Aberdeen Ave. SE
Kirtland AFB, NM 87117-5776
505-846-4823
505-846-4739
hague@alum.mit.edu
erika.siegenthaler@kirtland.af.mil
julia.rothman@kirtland.af.mil

Abstract—The Air Force Research Laboratory’s investment in revolutionary microsatellite (<225lb/100 kg) technologies has made it possible to consider space missions that provide true military utility. Unfortunately, there exists no method of employing these systems in a manner responsive to failure or crisis. This paper explores a microsatellite launch vehicle (MSLV) design, which can enable responsive space capability. Through the conceptual design of a 3-stage F-15 launched MSLV, concept feasibility is established based on current technology. Then, a test program is detailed to validate integrated aircraft/MSLV performance providing preliminary results and flight clearance analysis. Finally, through the application of advanced propulsion, guidance and navigation, and materials technologies, future MSLV capabilities are extracted to assess near-term microsatellite mission capabilities and cost.

mission applications are predicated on the ability to rapidly respond to unpredictable events in space. Currently there is limited ability to respond to a mission requiring rapid spacelift capabilities [1]. While there has been a focus on research and development into microsatellite technology, the existing technology means a long lead-time to mission completeness. The long time for integration and testing of a satellite and launch vehicle, coupled with the lack of a dedicated launch vehicle, and satellite system mean a limited ability for a timely response.

The aim of the F-15 MSLV is to enable a rapid response capability answering an identified need. The initial focus will be on enabling small (<450 lb/200 kg) payloads to a low earth orbit (LEO). This will lead to an affordable, dedicated launch and satellite capability with the additional benefit of a mobile launch site for accessibility to any orbit leading the way in rapid spacelift response.

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When comparing the F-15 MSLV concept to Pegasus, the leading small launch vehicle, the advantages of the F-15 MSLV become apparent. Pegasus needs a 50,000 lb satellite launch vehicle (SLV) to deliver a 500 lb (225 kg) satellite to a LEO orbit. The aircraft carrying Pegasus, an L-1011 carrier aircraft, has to be dedicated solely to the task of launching Pegasus. Comparatively, the F-15 MSLV weighs 10,000 lb, a fifth of the weight of Pegasus, and can deliver a microsatellite into LEO. Such a massive conservation of weight translates directly into cost savings; the Pegasus has a cost of approximately \$15 - \$30 Million per launch, while the F-15 MSLV is projected to be \$5 Million per launch. Projections of the F-15 MSLV payload

1. MOTIVATION

Rapid spacelift capability has become the focus of several research and development efforts [1]. This change in the launch paradigm is due in large part to the development and maturation of microsatellite technologies. However, these

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mass fraction were found to be a factor of 5 better than Pegasus (F-15 MSLV had a payload mass fraction of 0.02 while Pegasus has 0.004 when putting the same sized microsatellite into LEO). Pegasus has a launch processing time of 65 days, substantially longer than the projected 48 hours needed for the F-15 MSLV.

Microsatellite Capability

AFRL and DARPA have on-going programs to develop necessary technologies for microsatellites. The launch vehicle presented in this paper builds on the foundation of past AFRL research in microsatellite applications, which postulates that microsatellites are small, mass producible, low cost, and highly capable toward a single purpose. They are configured to accommodate a variety of missions, and have excess capability for the mission at hand. These satellites can be modular with a common bus and interchangeable payloads, and are storable either on the ground or on-orbit in dormant states. The size, adaptability and storability of these systems allow them to be mission configured and launched within hours of the employment decision [1]. Upon launch or activation these satellites use their on-board propulsion and navigation systems to rendezvous with other space assets and perform a wide spectrum of missions.

Launch On-Demand (LOD) Definition

LOD is the capability to rapidly launch a satellite into a desired orbit [2]. For the purposes of this paper, the time from initial mission need to mission execution will characterize the responsiveness of the LOD capability, and the degree of ability to place a microsatellite in any orbit at anytime will establish the spacelift capability [2].

Microsatellite Launch Vehicle (MSLV) Concept

Currently, commercial or government systems have very limited ability to react to satellite anomalies or system failures in space. Those options that are present, primarily manned servicing missions, are very costly to the point that the repair mission costs more than the original system.

Both civil and military space systems can benefit a great deal from the ability to rapidly launch microsatellites. At the spacecraft level, microsatellite systems can be used to inspect primary system anomalies, as well as to upgrade hardware and replenish expendables, extending the service life of large and expensive systems. At the constellation level, single satellite failures can be replaced by gap-fill systems to provide partial service in lieu of complete service loss.

However, no launch systems have been investigated beyond initial concept feasibility. Any efforts that have been made were conducted without considering the trades involving an integrated aircraft/spacecraft launch-on-demand system. To

enable a responsive space mission, the fundamental manner in which system level design is approached must be changed. This paper presents a system level concept for enabling responsive space capability that treats the MSLV as though it were a missile that is mass producible, storable, quickly processed, operationally benign to its aircraft platform, and cost effective.

MSLV Performance Goals

The conceptual design of a 3-stage, F-15 launched MSLV presented here is based on the use of commercial off the shelf (COTS) technology to reduce system non-recurring and recurring costs. The performance goal is to place 225lb of payload (36" x 30" right circular cylinder) into 150 NM circular, polar orbit within 48 hours of mission call-up.

Compatible Microsatellite Concept

The design and operation of the MSLV is based on the microsatellite concept developed by Kevin Bell and Ruth Moser in the study of conceptual designs for an on-demand microsatellite and air launched launch vehicles [1]. In this concept, a microsatellite is intended to perform a single-purpose, short-duration mission. Although this type of system is not as capable as a larger system, significant cost reductions are realized in satellite development and construction by limiting system robustness and capability.

Utility in a microsatellite system is achieved by developing a common bus that is capable of supporting multiple payloads and accomplishing multiple missions. The common bus and interchangeable payloads not only allow the microsatellite to be adapted for a specific mission, but also lend themselves to mass production and reduced system cost. Joint ASTEC-Industry studies have shown that it is possible to mass-produce microsatellite buses, which are storable and achieve 10x savings when compared to a larger system's total cost [3].

Responsive Space Notional Scenario

Utilizing the dual concepts of COTS and mass producibility, LOD satellites will be stored in pre-configured states on the ground. On mission call-up, the satellites are flight-readied and integrity-checked, loaded onto the MSLV placed into launch configuration in the air at the desired longitude and latitude, and launched. Then the satellites are deployed, checked out on-orbit, and start the mission profile. The total time from call-up to mission initiation is capable of being less than 48 hours.

Each mission begins with a command to rendezvous with a particular ephemeris element set for a specific object. The microsatellite determines its ephemeris using GPS, and propagates the ephemeris using on-board models. Then it calculates and performs a rendezvous trajectory using its

considerable on-board propulsion. LOD satellites can be launched to minimize rendezvous time or propellant use for a particular orbit. The rendezvous time varies depending on the customer satellite orbit. The microsatellite uses on-board sensors (visible, LIDAR, RF ranging) to acquire the customer satellite and, upon authentication, to perform various, final proximity maneuvers depending on its mission. Upon mission completion, the microsatellite either maneuvers to a safe orbit and goes dormant, or de-orbits itself.

2. MSLV DESIGN

Figure 1 - F-15 MSLV

MSLV Design Requirements

The MSLV is a three-stage, 10,000lb rocket designed to deliver a 225 lb (100 kg) satellite into LEO, as shown in Figure 1. These initial design requirements mean the operational MSLV is driven by the payload volumetric and mass to orbit goals, as well as the functional requirements of the MSLV and the F-15 interface. The initial design objective was to establish physical dimensions and mass properties of various MSLV configurations. After determination of the more promising designs, which were driven by payload requirements and MSLV functional requirements, possible configurations were evaluated with regard to F-15 interface requirements.

The volume of the MSLV is driven by the motor sizes, the available space beneath the F-15E and the desired payload volume. Initially, sizes and dimensions assigned to the motors and nozzle assemblies included high safety margins; these were subsequently reduced to eliminate interferences with the F-15.

Fundamental payload parameters were driven by the above requirements and the payload volume was established as 36" long, with a diameter of 30". The MSLV has a maximum weight of 10,000 lb, which is driven by the F-15 power capability and structural integrity. The load induced by the 10,000 lb MSLV on the centerline pylon and aircraft was found to be within acceptable safety parameters, despite modifications to the standard SUU-60 pylon that were necessary to accommodate the MSLV configuration [4].

MSLV Design

The final design MSLV was chosen because it providing the greatest performance capabilities, while satisfying volume, mass and center of gravity constraints.

Propulsion—A full range of configurations employing candidate motors were evaluated and optimized to meet volumetric, mass and center of gravity constraints. The solid rocket motors provided the desirable conditions of lowest inertial weight and shortest stage length for total impulse when compared with alternatives. The three-stage configuration was evaluated as providing the greatest payload to orbit. The initial findings found the use of the Star 48 as first stage motor offers the best performance to orbit within the volume and mass constraints set for the vehicle. The proposed Stage 1 motor, the Star 48 AV, is an 8" stretch case version of the Star 48V motor; this is a vectorable version of the Star 48B motor. Following the Star 48AV's successful static test it was selected as the stage 1 motor. Figure 2 clearly outlines the definition of each stage.

The Star 37GV and the Star 30BV were chosen based on their performance capabilities and the MSLV center of gravity requirements. The Star 37 GV, the selected stage 2 motor, has a graphite-epoxy case and is a vectorable version of the Star 37 motor with titanium cases. The Star 37GV flight motor will have a lighter weight casing and insulation.

The Star 30BV is a vectorable version of the Star 30B. With the goal of reduction in weight all three rocket motors have nozzles of a carbon-carbon exit cone.

Analysis shows that the Star 48AV/Star 37GV/Star 30BV is the optimal combination of all motors to meet performance goals, volumetric and mass constraints.

Electrical System—A custom chassis that can house the COTS components is needed for the electrical system. The custom chassis features simple design, ease of integration, reparability and wiring, reducing the overall system weight.

Figure 2 - F-15 MSLV Ignition Stages

Utilizing recent advances in pyrotechnic system technology, new designs have lowered the overall energy consumption, weight and testing requirements of electrical systems. Standard ordnance event devices are modified to use a “smart” initiator controlled from a central processor, leading to a “smart” logic ordnance compound and control device with low power consumption.

Smart initiators are given a unique ID and have a capacitor that charges when armed. With the controller enabled and ID smart initiator armed, the controller sends a unique memory address of the device to detonate. The current to ignite the pyrotechnic device comes from a rapid discharge, meaning power savings as well as the ability for the CPU to test ordnance devices.

Guidance, Navigation and Control—Traditionally Thrust Vector Control (TVC) systems are large, heavy and difficult to mount on a small vehicle. Identified as possible TVC solutions were the Pegasus TVC, Mach Controller, Comet TVC and TSRM TVC. The new TVC system will update the original Comet TVC system while keeping the same functionality and control as the original unit.

An attitude control system will provide roll control through flight and, if needed, pitch and yaw control between the motor burns. It will consist of 2 triads of reaction thrusters located on opposite sides of the avionics module.

Aircraft Integration Considerations—The pylon is the interface between the MSLV and the F-15, but due to MSLV requirements, it is necessary to include a modified SUU-60 pylon with the MSLV as one package. To make the MSLV/pylon operationally benign, the modified pylon has the same interface to the F-15 as the unmodified pylon. The pylon is a modified SUU-60 of skin and stringer type construction. The modified pylon employs the same design except the center portion is grooved along the underside to accommodate the MSLV. The pylon is reinforced along the mid-section to accommodate for the reduced depth of the cross-section. The interior plumbing and hardware associated with fuel transfer is removed and the harness is rerouted as required to allow for a release mechanism to be situated above the Stage 2 aft ring. The release mechanism is packaged where the MAU-12 currently attaches to the pylon. The pylon rigging mechanism assembly position remains unchanged, as well as the positions of the yaw

restraint tee, the aft pivot ball and the aircraft-to-pylon interface electrical connectors.

Validation of MSLV Design

Load and stress analyses were performed on the primary load bearing structure to include the Stage 1/Stage 2 (S1/2) interstage, the Stage 2/Stage 3 (S2/3) interstage, the avionics module/payload adaptor and fairing. This helped considerably in sizing the major structural elements of the MSLV. The load cases focused on the assembly, transport and handling; captive carry; release and free-fall; power flight and take off and landing with the MSLV.

These cases were evaluated to ensure the stress levels on various primary structures are within reasonable limits (the most stressful case during assembly, transport and handling happens when the store is cantilevered off the dolly during transport and aircraft pylon mate operations), this stress case is less than other stress cases the MSLV will experience during flight.

During captive carry the MSLV will experience inertial and drag induced loads. Once the stage 1 motor is fired the plume eliminates the base drag portion of the MSLV's total drag. During powered flight the MSLV will experience thrust vector, inertial and drag loads. During captive carry the loads are reacted through the forward and aft pylon attach points to the vehicle at the stage 2 aft ring and stage 1 aft boss. No drag coefficients are available for the vehicle while it is attached to the aircraft, however, it is assumed the drag loads are similar to those encountered during free fall with no plume influences [4].

Payload fairing deployment is to be performed during the Stage 1/2 coast period. This effectively treats the entire fairing as Stage 2 mass. There is a 2 second delay between drop and Stage 1 ignition, which allows the F-15 to gain sufficient clearance from the launch vehicle.

Significant analysis has been performed to ensure that the MSLV with the modified pylon will fit underneath the F-15E with adequate minimum clearances for the landing gear. The spacing between the ground and MSLV was examined to meet the clearance requirement imposed in the event of landing with a flat tire and collapsed strut. The analysis showed no interference or clearance issues with respect to the main landing gear doors or the bottom of the aircraft.

3. F-15 / MSLV FLIGHT TEST

Test Program Description

The Air Force Flight Test Center is to execute a flight test to support the certification testing of the Orbital MSLV test store. The purpose of the flight test is to establish the feasibility of Orbital's MSLV design with a captive carry test. The MSLV store to be used during this test is representative of the size, shape and weight of the planned launch vehicle.

In order for the MSLV store to become certified on the F-15E, captive carry and simulator tests will be performed. Initial testing in January 2003 will examine only the captive carry requirement. The MSLV test store will not include tail fins. When the operational MSLV is designed, the tail fins will be sized appropriately.

Drawing on Boeing predictions, directional stability of the clean F-15E with centerline mounted MSLV is higher than a clean F-15E with centerline tank for airspeeds up to 1.6M [5]. Above this speed the directional stability of the clean F-15E with centerline mounted MSLV has less directional stability than the F-15E with a centerline tank, however during the simulator testing in May 2002, it was found to have acceptable directional stability for aircraft handling abilities [5].

Test Objectives

The near term goal is to determine if the F-15E with MSLV can achieve the desirable launch condition. Optimal launch conditions have been ascertained as FL 380, 1.7 Mach and a flight path angle of 60°, all analyzed as ideal for launching a 225lb payload into LEO [6]. To facilitate this determination, the Air Force Flight Test Center will qualitatively evaluate the performance and handling qualities of an F-15E equipped with F-100-PW-229 (PW 229) engines and a centerline mounted MSLV store at critical points within the proposed launch profile during a captive flight test profile.

Ultimately the goal is to develop a system capable of putting a 450 lb (200 kg) satellite into LEO; this advanced technology would have integrated high payoff rocket propulsion technology (IHRPT) and a supersonic F-15 release.

Performance estimates were generated using 3 DOF simulations and using the trajectory optimization tool POST (Program Optimize Simulated Training) [6]. The performance partials for the MSLV are given in Table 1.

Table 1 – Performance partials associated with drop conditions

Drop Condition	Performance Partial
Altitude	+1 lbm : +1000 ft
Mach Number	+5 lbm : +0.1 Mach
Flight Path Angle	-1 lbm : -2°

Until drop conditions are fully validated by the flight test it is important to understand the potential performance sensitivity in drop conditions. Analysis has shown that the payload is most sensitive to changes in the speed at the drop condition, as outlined in Table 1.

4. SUMMARY

Microsatellite technology is an innovative and cost-effective answer to the need for greater capability and ensured U.S. responsiveness in space. The launch vehicle concept presented in this paper is a cost effective means for enabling responsive mission applications of microsatellites. Together, the MSLV and microsatellite provide a highly adaptable system capable of addressing the full spectrum of civil and military missions.

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